

INDIGO - DataCloud

RIA-653549

Data Management Plans and Data Life Cycle Support solutions over a Cloud Computing Framework: INDIGO-DataCloud

Presented by Fernando Aguilar (IFCA-CSIC)

aguilarf@ifca.unican.es

IDCC – 20th February 2017

INDIGO-DataCloud is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme

CSIC

CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

Context: Lifewatch

- **Research Community: LifeWatch (ERIC)**

- Topic/Area: Biodiversity & Ecosystem research

- **Objectives:**

- Provide **advanced capabilities** for research on the complex **biodiversity** system.

- **E-Infrastructure:**

- Resources: access to computing resources, data from physical infrastructures, services. For distributed centers and single research groups.

- **Capabilities:**

- Tackle big questions in biodiversity, societal challenges on biodiversity or ecosystems.
- Examples: Environmental Monitoring, Citizen Science initiatives, Species (identification, alien, etc.), ecosystem analysis (satellite data), etc.

Context: INDIGO-DataCloud Project

- **INDIGO = INtegrating Distributed data Infrastructures for Global Exploitation**
- H2020 project, Apr 2015 – Oct 2017, 11M EURO
- **26** partners in **11** European countries
- **Objectives:** Develop a data/computing platform, targeting various scientific communities and deployable on hybrid (private or public) Cloud infrastructures
- **Website:** <https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu>

INDIGO Architecture

- Enhanced features in
 - IaaS
 - PaaS
 - SaaS
- 1st release **MidnightBlue**
 - Data Center Solutions
 - Data Solutions
 - Automated Solutions
 - High-level User Oriented Solutions

INDI Arch

Access & Usability

High level application portals and mobile applications

- Enhance
- Improve
- Performance
- Scalability
- 1st response
- Data
- Data
- Analytics
- Tools
- Services

Data Center and Storage solutions

Services and solutions allowing data and compute resource centers to increase efficiency for customers

Fairshare Scheduler for OpenStack

Cloud Provider Ranker

Global Data Access

Infrastructure Manager

Storage Quality of Service and Data Lifecycle Support

Partition Director Service for Batch and Cloud resources

Extended OpenStack and OpenNebula Functionalities

OCCl Support for OpenStack and OpenNebula

User-oriented solutions

Services and solutions to improve the QoS user experience

Userspace Container Support

Data Mining and Analytics for e Science Server

Indigo Plug-ins for scientific workflow systems

Future Gateway (Programmable Scientific Portal)

Automated solutions

A rich set of high-level automated functionalities for Data Centers and customers

PaaS Orchestrator

QoS/SLA Management Service

Core PaaS

Authentication and Authorization service

User Authentication

Solutions Developed for Data support

- **OneData – Global Data Access**

- Data management system providing easy access to distributed storage resources. Supports from data management to data-intensive scientific computations.
- Data stored in multiple sites, accessing different ways: web, POSIX, etc.

- **Storage QoS (Quality of Service)**

- This solution implements the INDIGO-DataCloud CDMI Server, a set of functionalities aimed at Improving QoS capabilities of storage resources for better support of high-level storage requirements.
- Rules definition for indicating storage behavior: site, network connection, type of storage, etc.
- As standard, the CDMI server will support multiple storage back-ends like dCache, Ceph, GPFS, Gemss+TSM, StoRM and HPSS.

- **Both Components are being integrated.**

INDIGO Data Life Cycle Support

INDIGO Data Life Cycle Support

INDIGO Data Life Cycle Support

FAIR+R!

Tool Integration is needed!

INDIGO Data Life Cycle Support

• DMPTool

- Project Context
- Instrumentation, data sources.
- Dataset structure, definition, attributes, etc.
- Publish itself, and link to published datasets.
- Added features:
 - Taxonomy import: Attribute definition, species repository, etc.
 - Automatic publication on Open Science Preservation Framework.

INDIGO Data Life Cycle Support

• OSPF

- Data Life Cycle Management.
- Link to Storage/Computing
- Not only Datasets: software, DMPs, Analysis.
- Linked to DataCite to get DOI. Internal PID.
- Linked to computing (VMs, Docker).

Overview and Demo

• Integration

- Prototype (Demo)
- Using both APIs for communication.
- Publish DMP in portal
- Publish Datasets, Software at DMP.
- Define Data Integrity test at DMP, at different levels:
 - Check existence
 - Metadata
 - Data processing test (Dataset + Software).

Thank you!

<https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu>
Better Software for Better Science.

Fernando Aguilar (IFCA-CSIC)
aguilarf@ifca.unican.es

